

Effect of goat breeds on the milk composition under climatic conditions of Baswa tehsil of Dausa district Rajasthan

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Abstract

Milk is often rightly described as a near-complete food in nature. It contains all five major nutrients: fat, protein, lactose (milk sugar), vitamins, and minerals (salts). The research was conducted at the Rukmani Devi College of Agriculture, Dausa district of Rajasthan during 2021-23. The specific gravity of the Sirohi goat milk was greater than that of Jakhrana animals. The overall fat percent in both breeds during 2021- 23 of all the 1200 samples was found to be 4.61 ± 0.021 , Solids Not Fat (SNF) 8.44 ± 0.030 percent, and total solids percentage was found to be 13.32 ± 0.035 . The protein percent during 2021 - 22 conditions was significantly ($p < 0.01$) greater than that of farm-rearing goat milk in both breeds. The statistical analysis also revealed that the lactose content in 2021 – 22 has significantly higher than that of 2022 -23 in Jakhrana as well as Sirohi goat breeds at $p < 0.05$. The average ash content in both breeds' milk during 2021 - 23 of all samples was found to be 0.814 ± 0.007 percent. Breed had conspicuous effects on milk quality of goats under study.

Keywords: Goat breeds, milk composition, Dausa, Rajasthan

Introduction

The Jakhrana breed is found in the north-west arid and semi-arid regions mainly in eastern Rajasthan. The breed derives its name from the Jakhrana village in Alwar district where it is found in its purest form. They are large animals. The coat is predominantly black with white spots on the ears and the muzzle is short and lustrous. The face line is straight, with a narrow and slightly bulging forehead. The breed looks similar to the Beetal, the major difference being that the Jakhrana is taller. The ear length is medium and the udder is large, with conical teats. Does are reared for milk. A majority of the bucks are sold for meat, with a small number retained for breeding (Verma et al, 2004).

Goat population of our country increased from 47.14 million in the year 1951 to 124.5 million in 2005 (Singh and Sharma, 2013). The gir breed which is rated as a relatively better milk producer of indigenous breed's needs exploration of its production potentiality to know its further

prospects. Improvement can be made through proper management, feeding, handling, and other environmental conditions which will influence the expression of characters but a limit of which is set by the heredity of the individual (Singh et al 2013). Goats are an integral part of livestock production and play a vital role in the socio-economic structure of rural poor. This study aimed to project the importance and significance of goat milk with special reference to Indian fields and farm-rearing conditions. There are adverse ecological and physiological constraints in the Indian system of goat farming. Goat population of our country increased from 47.14 million in the year 1951 to 124.5 million in 2005 (Singh and Sharma, 2014).

The global goat population currently stands at 921 million, of which over 90% are found in developing countries. Asia is home to about 60% of the total world goat population and has the largest goat breed share of 26%. Goats play a vital socio-economic role in Asian agriculture, particularly for resource-poor people living in harsh environments. Non-cattle milk accounts for approximately 15% of the total milk consumption by humans worldwide (Singh et al 2014). India today, stands first in the area of milk production at the world level, with an annual growth rate of about 4%. The country's milk production in 2010 was estimated to be 110 million tonnes. A large quantity of milk produced in the country amounting to over 46% is being consumed as liquid milk. The production and use of animal products in the use of human diet is receiving tremendous attention. With this object in view, the need for developing Animal Husbandry is recognized very well. The other objects are to provide animal power for farming and adoption of better land use patterns (Singh et al 2012). The productive improvements among dairying animals can be made through proper management, feeding and handling, etc. which may influence the expression of productive characters as per its heritability nature. Before identifying the animals for breeding and production purposes screening of animals shall be performed based on physical traits (Singh et al 2013). Various government and non-government organizations have also recognized the importance of poultry farming as employment generating enterprise and are engaged in motivating more and more entrepreneurs to take up this enterprise (Singh et al 2014). Goats play a vital socio-economic role in Asian agriculture, particularly for resource-poor people living in harsh environments (Singh et al 2014).

Fig. 1 Map showing location of Baswa tehsil of Dausa district Rajasthan

Goats are more often poorly managed and this is attributed to their ability to survive under harsh conditions and also because most people in rural areas rear goats for their subsistence purposes to support their families. This benefit is often not shown in national statistics because of informal trading and slaughtering (Singh et al 2014). Goat milk contains less lactose than cow's milk, so is less likely to trigger lactose intolerance (Singh et al 2014). Goat meat is a high-quality protein source is the choicest meat in the domestic market (Singh et al 2014).

Major population of India primarily depends on the agricultural-based system for their daily life including goat keeping which constitutes an important rural business of small marginal farmers and landless laborers (Singh et al 2014). Reproductive management of an animal is governed by several parameters, viz. age at first conception, age at first calving, and first gestation length, etc. (Singh et al 2014). Goat milk contains less lactose than cow's milk, so it is less likely to trigger lactose intolerance (Singh and Sharma, 2015). It has since played a significant socioeconomic role in the evolution of human civilization around the world (Singh and Sharma, 2015). Farmers felt that grass is more useful to fill the animals' stomachs and would therefore come before crop stover as feed. Farmers preferred Deda over Kona because it has more biomass (Singh and Sharma, 2015).

A very important aspect in this regard is the awareness of risk by resource-poor farmers and their emphasis on minimizing it (Singh and Sharma, 2016). The country is endowed with a large and biologically diverse population of goats. (Singh and Sharma, 2016).

The nutritional value of milk is closely related to its composition, which is affected by factors such as breed, diet, stage of lactation, season etc. Goat milk has more calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), magnesium (Mg), and chloride (Cl) and less sodium (Na) and sulfur (S) content than cow milk (Singh and Sharma, 2016). Livestock production is the backbone of Indian agriculture contributing 7% to the national GDP and source of employment and livelihood for 70% population in rural areas. India ranks first in terms of milk production (129.7 million tons) (Singh et al 2017). Animals reared in intensive production systems consume a considerable amount of protein and other nitrogen-containing substances in their diets (Singh et al 2017). This benefit is often not shown in national statistics because of informal trading and slaughtering (Singh and Sharma, 2017).

Goats play a vital socioeconomic role in Asian agriculture, particularly for resource-poor people living in harsh environments (Singh et al 2018). Jamnapari (or Jamunapari) is a breed of goat originating from the Indian subcontinent. Since 1953 they have been imported to Indonesia (popular as Etawa goat, and its mixture with a local goat called "PE", Peranakan Etawa or Etawa mix) where they have been a great success (Singh et al 2017).

These breeds or types were distributed across the world as a result of the migration and translocation of humans, usually due to changing climatic conditions and natural resources (Singh and Sharma, 2017). Milk-secreting tissues and various ducts throughout the udder can be damaged by bacterial toxins, and sometimes permanent damage to the udder occurs (Singh and Singh, 2020). Livestock has become an integral part of all interventions aimed at reducing rural poverty and enhancing food and nutrition security (Singh and Somvanshi, 2020). India is endowed with a significant share of the world's livestock population growing steadily and continuously (Singh, G. 2019). The goat is thought to have been the earliest domesticated ruminant and of all the species of domesticated animals except the dog, has the widest ecological range (Singh, G., 2024). Man, Animal, and Nature are in a symbiotic relationship for their survival and sustenance (Singh et. al., 2024).

Fig. 2 Jakhrana and Sirohi Goat

Fig. 3 Electronic Milk Analyzer

METHODOLOGY

The research has conducted at the Rukmani Devi College of Agriculture, Dausa district of Rajasthan with a broad objective, as 'Effect of goat breeds on the milk composition under climatic conditions of Baswa tehsil of Dausa district Rajasthan during 2021-23. 05 milk samples of Sirohi goat and 05 milk samples were collected from the Jakhrana goat breed during the lactation at different villages of Baswa tehsil of the Dausa district throughout two years. A total of 1200 (600 and 600) samples were collected from both goat breeds of Baswa tehsil. All samples were analyzed by an electronic milk analyzer.

Results and Discussion

1. Effect of Goat breeds on Specific gravity:-

The data obtained on specific gravity in the present study of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed milk are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Effect of Goat breeds on Specific gravity of milk.

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t)	
						5%	1%
1.	Jakhrana	1.0123±0.0003	1.0132±0.0003	1.012±0.0003	3.51 ⁺	1.540	2.145
2.	Sirohi	1.0196±0.0002	1.0163±0.0003	1.0179±0.0002	3.20 ⁺		
	Overall mean	1.0159±0.0002	1.0147±0.0002	1.0240±0.0002			

Note: + = Significant at 5% level of significance

It is observed from Table 1. that the specific gravity of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds has found to be 1.0123±0.0003 and 1.0196±0.0002, respectively with an average of 1.0159±0.0002. It is observed from above table that specific gravity of Sirohi goat breed's milk has greater than that of Jakhrana animals.

2. Effect of Goat breeds on Fat %:-

The result obtained for the fat percentage of milk of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - Effect of Goat breeds on Fat % of milk.

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t)	
						5%	1%

1.	Jakhrana	4.41±0.034	4.71±0.033	4.51±0.032	2.987 ⁺	1.547	2.321
2.	Sirohi	4.81±0.087	4.81±0.023	4.81±0.011	2.354 ⁺⁺		
	Overall mean	4.61±0.060	4.71±0.046	4.61±0.021			

Note: + = Significant at $p < 0.05$

++=Significant at $p < 0.01$

The average percentage of fat in the milk of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds has found to be 4.41±0.034 and 4.81±0.087 respectively with an average value of 4.61±0.060 per cent during 2021 - 22 Similarly, fat content in 2022 - 23 of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds has found to be 4.71±0.033 and 4.81±0.023, respectively with an average value of 4.71±0.046 per cent. The overall fat per cent in the both breeds during 2021- 23 of all the 1200 samples has found to be 4.61±0.021. The results of the present investigation on fat content of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds are in consonance with the observation of Singh and Sharma (2015), Prasad et. al. (2005) have, however, reported higher value for fat percentage of goat milk. Lower values have been reported by Agnihotri et. al. (2002).

3. Effect of Goat breeds on Protein %:-

The data on Protein percentage in the present investigation of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed's milk during 2021 - 23 are recorded in Table 3.

Table 3 - Effect of Goat breeds on Protein % of milk

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t) 5% 1%
1.	Jakhrana	3.18±0.028	3.11±0.034	3.14±0.032	5.875 ⁺⁺	1.960 2.576
2.	Sirohi	3.19±0.027	3.13±0.036	3.11±0.032	4.51 ⁺⁺	
	Overall mean	3.13±0.028	3.12±0.035	3.15±0.32		

Note: ++ = Significant at $p < 0.01$

It is observed from the Table 3 that the protein percentage in the Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds during 20 – 21 has found to 3.18±0.028 and 3.11±0.034, respectively with an average of 3.13±0.028 per cent. The protein content of aforesaid breeds during 2022 - 23 found to be 3.11±0.034 and 3.13±0.036 per cent respectively with an average value of 3.12±0.035 per cent. It is clear from the above table that protein per cent during 2021 - 22 has significantly ($p < 0.01$) greater than that of 2022 -23 goat milk in both the breeds. The statistical analysis revealed that protein content of Jakhrana goat breed has significantly higher than that of Sirohi goat breed during 2021 - 22. The analysis of variance of these data (Table 3) revealed that protein content variation either Jakhrana or Sirohi goat breeds had significant ($p < 0.05$) effect during 2021 - 23.

4. Effect of Goat breeds on Lactose %:-

The lactose per cent in the milk of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds during 2021 - 23 in the present investigation are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 - Effect of Goat breeds on Lactose % of milk.

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t)	
						5%	1%
1.	Jakhrana	4.29 ±0.021	4.20±0.022	4.25±0.021	1.859 ⁺	1.960	2.576
2.	Sirohi	4.27 ±0.020	4.23±0.025	4.21±0.022	1.243 ⁺		
	Overall mean	4.23±0.0205	4.215±0.0235	4.23±0.014			

Note: + = Significant at $p < 0.05$

It is clear from Table 4 that the lactose content in Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed's milk during 2021 – 22 has found 4.29 ±0.021 and 4.27 ±0.020 per cent, respectively. Similarly the lactose content in above both breed milk during 2022 – 23 has found 4.20±0.022 and 4.23±0.025 per cent, respectively. The overall average lactose per cent in Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed's milk during 2021 - 23 also calculated and found to be 4.23±0.014 for all 1200 samples. The statistical analysis also revealed that the lactose content in 2021 – 22 has significantly higher than that of 2022 -23 in Jakhrana as well as Sirohi goat breeds at $p < 0.05$. Our results on lactose percentage in above goat breed's milk are in fair agreement with those reported by Prasad et. al. (2002) and Agnihotri (2002) have reported higher values on it.

5. Effect of Goat breeds on Ash %:-

The results obtained for ash content of Jhakarana as well as Sirohi goat milk during 2021 - 23 are presented in Table 5.

Table 5 - Effect of Goat breeds on Ash % of milk.

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t)	
						5%	1%
1.	Jakhrana	0.80±0.008	0.82±0.007	0.81±0.008	3.879 ⁺	1.960	2.576
2.	Sirohi	0.82±0.008	0.84±0.005	0.82±0.006	3.654 ⁺⁺		
	Overall mean	0.81±0.008	0.82±0.006	0.814±0.007			

Note: + = Significant at $p < 0.05$

++ = Significant at $p < 0.01$

The average percentage of ash during 2021 – 22 Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed's milk has found to be 0.80±0.008 and 0.82±0.008, respectively with an average value of 0.81±0.008 per cent. Similarly ash content in 2022 -23 of aforesaid breed's milk has found to be 0.82±0.007

and 0.84 ± 0.005 , per cent with an average of 0.82 ± 0.006 per cent. The overall average ash content in both breed's milk during 2021 - 23 of all samples has found to be 0.815 ± 0.007 per cent. It is also clear from the above table that ash content in the milk of Jakhrana or Sirohi goat breed 2022-23 has significantly greater than that of 2021-22. The analysis of variance table showed that ash content of Jakhrana goat breed's milk during 2022- 23 has significantly more than that of Sirohi goat breed milk. The results of present investigation on the level of ash in Jakhrana and Sirohi goats' milk during 2021 - 23 are slightly higher by the findings (0.78 ± 0.01) of Agnihotri et. al. (2002) and Singh and Sharma (2015).

6. Effect of Goat breeds on Total Solids %:-

The results obtained for total solids percentage in milk of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed during 2021 - 23 are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 - Effect of Goat breeds on Total solids % of milk.

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t)	
						5%	1%
1.	Jakhrana	13.03 ± 0.030	13.16 ± 0.035	13.09 ± 0.032	1.21 ⁺	1.960	2.576
2.	Sirohi	13.23 ± 0.036	13.87 ± 0.039	13.55 ± 0.037	1.985 ^{NS}		
	Overall mean	13.13 ± 0.033	13.51 ± 0.037	13.32 ± 0.035			

Note: NS = Non Significant

+ = Significant at $p < 0.05$

According to above Table 6, the average total solids percentage in milk of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed during 2021 – 22 has found to be 13.03 ± 0.030 and 13.23 ± 0.036 , respectively with an average value of 13.13 ± 0.033 . Similarly the total solids percentage in the milk of above goat breeds during 2022 – 23 has found to be 13.16 ± 0.035 and 13.87 ± 0.039 , respectively with an average value of 13.13 ± 0.037 per cent. The overall average total solids percentage of all 1200 samples has found to be 13.32 ± 0.035 . It has observed from above table that Jakhrana goat breed's milk total solids were significantly ($p < 0.050$) higher in 2021-22 than 2022-23 whereas in case of Sirohi goat breed an insignificant difference has observed in total solids content. The analysis of variance in the table revealed that the breed variation during 2021 -22 has non-significant but it has significant during 2022 -23 at 5% level of significance.

The level of total solids percentage in the milk of above goat's breeds as obtained in the present study, Compared favorably with the results of Pal et. al. (2011) and Agnihotri (2002). Prasad et. al. (2005) have, however, reported higher values of Singh and Sharma (2015).

7. Effect of Goat breeds on Solids-Not-Fat %:-

The data on solids-not-fat percentage in Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed's milk during 2021 - 23 are recorded in Table 7.

Table 7 - Effect of Goat breeds on Solids-Not-Fat % of milk.

Sl. No.	Breeds	2021 - 22	2022 -23	Overall average	Test of significance	Table value (t)	
						5%	1%
1.	Jakhrana	8.39±0.036	8.45±0.024	8.43±0.030	3.659 ⁺⁺	1.960	2.576
2.	Sirohi	8.46±0.034	8.48±0.026	8.47±0.030	3.854 ⁺⁺		
	Overall mean	8.42±0.035	8.46±0.025	8.44±0.030			

Note: ++ = Significant at $p < 0.01$

It is observed from Table 7 that the solids-not-fat percentage in the milk of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breeds during 2020 – 21 has been found to be 8.39±0.036 and 8.46±0.034, respectively with an average value of 8.42±0.035 percent. The solids-not-fat content of the above breeds during 2022 - 23 samples has also been calculated and found to be 8.45±0.024 and 8.48±0.026 percent, respectively with an average of 8.46±0.025 percent. The overall average solids-not-fat percentage of the above samples in 2021-22 and 2022 - 23 of all 1200 samples has 8.44±0.030 per cent. The statistical analysis showed that the solids-not-fat percentage has significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher in 2022-23 either the Jakhrana or Sirohi goat breed than that of 2021-22. It is due to higher fat percentage and lower percentage of protein, lactose, and ash in 2022-23 of Jakhrana as well as Sirohi goat breeds. The analysis of the variance table on these data also revealed that significant breed variation on solids-not-fat content has been observed either 2021-22 or 2022-23. The results of the present investigation on solids-not-fat content of Jakhrana and Sirohi goat breed's milk 2021-23 align with the slightly higher observations of Singh and Sharma, (2015).

Conclusion

The specific gravity and fat percentage in the milk of Jakhrana has significantly higher than the milk of Sirohi goat breeds. Breed had conspicuous effects on the milk quality of goats under study.

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